

Deliverable 6.3.2.1

REQUIREMENTS FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF DISTRIBUTED SIMULATION FOR
DISTRIBUTED ENERGY SYSTEMS

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Requirements for implementation of distributed simulation for distributed energy systems

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General Information

The following describes the context and purpose of the deliverable and how it fits into the NFDI4Energy framework.

Summary

Due to the increasing importance of renewable energies in Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (CPES), the interaction and coordination between all distributed instances is essential to efficiently manage the high volatility of generation and grid congestions at all grid levels. To simulate the distributed energy system, all instances need to be considered, such as Distributed Energy Resources (DER) simulators, agent simulators, and communication simulators. The delivery of flexibility must be considered from multiple grid levels, including lower voltage levels, as for redispatch based on market principles. In this context, the aggregation of flexibility is essential as well. Self-organization using autonomous agents within automation systems is key to adaptive and self-healing systems. Self-healing Multi-Agent System (MAS) can be applied to fulfill optimization within the grid while considering redispatch demands. As the communication infrastructure affects the system, for example by delays or packet drops, the functionality of the system needs to be ensured considering communication effects. Thus, research regarding the implementation of a distributed simulation for distributed energy systems covers multiple aspects, such as the coupling of simulators, self-healing aspects, effects from the communication infrastructure, flexibility delivery, and aggregation. The primary objective of this deliverable is to collect requirements for the simulation in this use case, covering all relevant aspects as listed above.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

The deliverable considers all software parts within the use case 6.3 for distributed simulation of the distributed energy system. Multiple types of software must be developed for the simulation and thus, specific requirements for the different software assets exist. The deliverable covers all the software assets developed or discussed in the use case. The following tasks are considered:

- Task 6.3.1: Derive a model of distributed flexibility
- Task 6.3.2: Develop self-healing flexibility aggregation
- Task 6.3.3: Analyze mechanisms for redispatch pools
- Task 6.3.4: Conduct communication network simulation
- Task 6.3.5: Implement aggregation-based management of flexibility

Deliverable

As the deliverable covers all aspects of simulation for the distributed energy system, the discussion of the deliverable is also structured based on these aspects. The requirements were collected in two phases. In the beginning, requirements regarding the first tasks (flexibility, coupling of simulators, autonomous systems) were collected, as these were starting with the development. Questions regarding these aspects contain specific data formats, interfaces, etc., and were collected regarding the software as considered a simulation service for NFDI4Energy. Later, another round of requirements was collected, including all tasks. Here, updates for the first tasks are considered and requirements were added, as these tasks were already implemented. The requirements are integrated into the requirements for simulation services for NFDI4Energy and are publicly available ¹.

a) Requirements for standardized flexibility representation

Flexibility is considered in the following list of requirements.

- 6.3.4: Flexibility and self-healing

As multiple types of DER are considered in this use case, the need for standardized flexibility is given. Here, it makes sense to consider one model that allows unified flexibility modeling of multiple DER, as described in [1]. When considering standardized flexibility representations, typical categories, and requirements of flexibility, need to be covered. For more details, we like to point out **Deliverable D6.3.1.2 Tutorial on flexibility modeling**. Here, we describe typical categories and requirements to consider when dealing with flexibility to provide it in a standardized way.

b) Requirements regarding the coupling of simulators

For the coupling of simulators, the implementation of a redispatch use case was taken into account, considering a neighborhood grid of DER, coordinated and managed by a MAS. The scenario was implemented based on the concepts in [2], [3], the implementation is described in detail here [4] and is publicly available ². The requirements are collected based on the given scenario and listed in the following.

- 6.3.3: Integration of different power plants as wind turbines, photo voltaic, combined heat and power, battery. All these plants are considered in the scenario.
- 6.3.6: The integration of a communication simulator to be able to consider the effects of the communication infrastructure.
- 6.3.8: Typical input data types, such as *csv* and *hdf5*
- 6.3.11: The reduction of the complexity of the coupling
- 6.3.13: Keeping the interface to other simulators easily interchangeable
- 6.3.15: Allow different execution variants (GUI, command line) and thus consider these in the coupling

c) Requirements for integration of autonomous systems based on distributed artificial intelligence

The requirements for integrating autonomous systems based on distributed artificial intelligence were collected based on integrating a MAS in the respective scenario. The requirements are listed in the following.

¹https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/simulation-service-requirements/blob/main/requirements/simulation_as_a_service.md

²<https://github.com/Digitalized-Energy-Systems/communication-incidents-in-cpes>

- 6.3.1: Agent-based systems should be considered in the simulation
- 6.3.5: Different types of agents, such as unit agents, aggregator agent and grid agent
- 6.3.12: The simulation of the message exchange of the agent system via the communication framework
- 6.3.14 Consider real and simulation time. When coupling agent frameworks to co-simulation frameworks, real-time consideration needs to be combined with simulation time, as described in [5]
- 6.3.17 Distributed optimization should be possible
- 6.3.18 Fast data exchange should be considered to fulfill use case constraints regarding run time
- 6.3.19 Evaluation scripts should be developed based on output data
- 6.3.20 Scalability of the autonomous distributed systems is necessary
- 6.3.21 Demands from the market should be considered, as in redispatch scenarios
- 6.3.22 Reactions to disturbances should be implemented in order to ensure the robustness of the system (self-healing)

d) Requirements regarding the need for communication simulation, configuration of distributed simulations for studying communications

The increasing integration of renewable energies, smart grid technologies, and decentralized generation leads to a growing interdependence between energy and communication networks. Modern energy systems rely on a robust and reliable communication infrastructure to exchange real-time data, optimize power flows, and coordinate grid-stabilizing measures. To systematically analyze these interactions using co-simulations, we identified the following requirements.

- 6.3.23: Defining message exchange format between the energy and communication domain (*XML*, *JSON*, object list, etc.)
- 6.3.24: Seamless integration of OMNeT++³ and ns-3⁴ into DaceDS middleware must be enabled.
- 6.3.25: Seamless integration of OpenDSS⁵ into DaceDS middleware must be enabled.

Adding support for new simulators

The following simulators represent the state of the art for modeling communication networks:

ns-3 [6]: ns-3 is a discrete-event network simulator, targeted primarily for research and educational use. ns-3 is free software, licensed under the GNU GPLv2 license, and is publicly available for research, development, and use. ns-3 supports a real-time scheduler that facilitates a number of “simulation-in-the-loop” use cases for interacting with real systems. For instance, users can emit and receive ns-3-generated packets on real network devices, and ns-3 can serve as an interconnection framework to add link effects between virtual machines [6].

OMNeT++ [7]: OMNeT++ is an extensible, modular, component-based C++ simulation library and framework, primarily for building network simulations. OMNeT++ is a public-source, component-based, modular and open-architecture simulation environment with strong GUI support. Its primary application area is the simulation of communication networks [7].

³<https://omnetpp.org/>

⁴<https://www.nsnam.org/>

⁵<https://opendss.epri.com/IntroductiontoOpenDSS.html>

e) Requirements for simulation settings using hierarchical aggregation concepts

Hierarchical aggregation can be understood as a structured way of managing flexibility assets, allowing scalable, decentralized operation while maintaining central coordination. It ensures that Electric Vehicles (EVs) and stationary batteries can contribute to power grid stability without violating individual constraints, also called "Flexibility" as in [8]. The goal is to balance scalability and constraint management. To assess the aggregation-based flexibility, the simulation must incorporate hierarchical aggregation concepts, based on [8]:

- 6.3.26: Simulation must support a multi-level aggregation approach where individual assets (EVs, stationary batteries) are grouped into sub-fleets, which then contribute to an aggregated flexibility.
- 6.3.27: Aggregation should include regional or zone to reflect real-world grid segmentation.
- 6.3.28: Simulation should integrate power, energy, and time constraints at the individual asset level to ensure that flexibility does not violate user-specific limitations.
- 6.3.29: Unidirectional versus bidirectional charging should be configurable to study their effects on flexibility potential.
- 6.3.30: Simulation must support large-scale EV fleets and stationary batteries, handling thousands to millions of assets.
- 6.3.31: Simulation must account for stochastic variations in mobility patterns, charging availability, and flexibility demand.
- 6.3.32: External factors such as weather conditions, grid disturbances, and market price fluctuations should be simulated to reflect realistic conditions.
- 6.3.33: Simulation has to be able to evaluate grid resilience by simulating communication failures and impaired data transmission

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